

Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme and Spin Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 3, 2021

In Part I of this note, we argued that the $\exp(ipx)$ portion of a free quantum particle's wavefunction follows from $d/dx A(x,t) = p$ extended to an eigenvalue equation: $-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ "p" appears as a scalar because it is the momentum magnitude, but one may consider flow in 3-space i.e. p_x, p_y, p_z . In such a case, one might think of using basis vectors e_i such that $e_i \cdot e_i = 1$ ($i=1,2,3$). Given that one has an operator equation, one uses basis operators or matrices instead leading to the Pauli matrices or 4x4 matrices as found by Dirac if one imposes the restriction that upon "squaring" the operators disappear because one only has pp .

As a result, we argued that intrinsic spin is linked to 3-space recognition for a free particle. The resulting spin, however, is spin $\frac{1}{2}$ so what about other spins say 0 or 1? This seems to imply that free recognition of 3-space does not apply to other spin cases as it does to spin $\frac{1}{2}$. The Stern-Gerlach experiment already shows that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is interesting in that one may have spin up or down project along any 3-space axis. In Part I, we showed that a wave-equation developed for the photon from d/dt (partial) b ($E|E| + BB$) + grad dot $E \times B = 0$ contains an e_{ijk} ($-i d/dx_i$) term with e_{ijk} being the Levi-Civita symbol as well as the spin matrix. This is not the Pauli matrix (or matrix containing it) and suggests a different geometry or basis scheme. Thus, there is physical angular momentum (spin) in a plane perpendicular to the momentum and the (1,0) spin component is "hidden", but associated with angular momentum in another spatial direction. As a result, 3-space is not treated in an independent way as in the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case. In this note, we investigate this idea further by considering the deuteron, He4 and He3 and try to argue that intrinsic spin still seems to have a connection to 3-space recognition, but that the fully independent 3-space recognition corresponds to spin $\frac{1}{2}$. We only consider spin 0, $\frac{1}{2}$ and 1 in this note.

Spin and Recognition of 3-Space

P. Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation to obtain a linear equation corresponding to a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle. At first glance, one may ask: Why should the linear equation only correspond to spin $\frac{1}{2}$? In Part I, we began with the idea d/dx (partial) $A(x,t) = p$ where $A(x,t)$ is the free particle action = $t L$ written with $v=x/t$. After differentiation, x/t may be set back to v . If one writes this in terms of an eigenvalue equation then:

$$-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((1a)) \text{ where } A = -Et + px \quad (\text{Note: } d/dt \text{ (partial) } A = -E \text{ so } id/dt \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA))$$

There is no spin present in ((1a))((1b)) and these two may be used to construct either the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equations which have no spin. (Note: E and p differ for the nonrelativistic/relativistic cases.)

In order to introduce spin, we argued in Part I that one may consider p_x, p_y, p_z instead of p which is the magnitude. If one has a vector p , one would normally use basis vectors e_i such that $e_i \cdot e_i = 1$ ($i=1,2,3$). In the case of an eigenvalue equation, one uses operators and so not only does one have an operator for p_x i.e. $-i\hbar/dx$, but also for e_i , namely $a(i)$ i.e. a matrix. Imposing the constraint that the basis operators disappear upon squaring, one has a constraint equation which leads to the Pauli matrices or 4×4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices as P. Dirac showed. This seems to be a completely general argument, namely independent 3-space recognition, but it only yields spin (linked to the eigenvectors of the matrices) of $\frac{1}{2}$. This immediately begs two questions? Where is angular momentum and what about other spins such as spin 0 or 1?

Traditionally the link between spin and angular momentum followed from the Stern-Gerlach experiment in which an electron has an intrinsic moment which interacts with a magnetic field. Classically this suggests a current or internal angular momentum, but the Pauli matrices are mathematical expressions linked to two choices (up, down) and 3-space independence. Thus two different things seem to be occurring. From $\exp(ipx)$ one sees that linear space resolution depends on motion i.e. on p . If one expects an electron to recognize 3-space apart from any linear motion, one might expect an internal motion contained within the size of the electron. Given the idea of uncertainty of space in quantum mechanics, this seems to imply angular momentum e.g. spin up and down. In fact in (1) spin is described as momentum flow in the wavefunction. We suggest that this flow is also linked to 3-space recognition, but the completely independent case of this seems to only be spin $\frac{1}{2}$. What happens in the case of spin 0 and spin 1?

Spin 0

Spin 0 particles such as He4 are said to be described by the Klein-Gordon equation which only contains p i.e. the magnitude of momentum p . There is no sense of flow or flux in 3 space even though the equation may be obtained from two flux/flow equations $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ and $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ where $A = -Et + px$. To try to see why there is no 3-space recognition, consider the deuteron which contains two fermions. For spin 0, there is correlation i.e. spin up and down or vice versa so there is no independent result of up or down in one or 3 dimensions. We argue that this freedom of up/down type angular momentum (i.e. circling to the right or left) in all 3 dimensions yields 3-space recognition, so for spin 0 this recognition is lost.

Spin 1

Spin 1 is interesting in that it exists for a massless particle, the photon, as well as for the deuteron which consists of two spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles. In the case of the photon, one may obtain an equation analogous to the Dirac equation from $\frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) (E|E| + B|B|)a + b \text{ grad} \cdot E \times B = 0$ by pulling out $E + iB$ (vectors) (see Part I). (E is the electric field and B the magnetic.) This leaves an equation linear in $E + iB$ (the wavefunction) which contains a term $\epsilon_{ijk} (-i\hbar/dx_i)$ where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol. Thus ϵ_{ijk} and not the Pauli matrices (or 4×4 matrices containing the Pauli matrices) represent spin. This spin is physical angular motion of energy in a plane perpendicular to the momentum for circularly polarized light, but there is still the (1,0) spin

component which is not manifest. Thus, one does not see a completely independent 3-space recognition. Rather (1,1) and (1,-1) are linked to a plane perpendicular to momentum and (1,0) suggests a third direction. For a given axis, there are projections along this axis, but another projection (1,0) as well. As a result, assuming independent 3-space recognition may not apply for spin 1. (In fact, it does not because linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation or suggesting that $\{a(j) (-id/dxj)\} \{a(j) (-id/dxj)\}$ lead to $-d/dxd/dx -d/dyd/dy -d/dz d/dz$ only corresponds to spin $\frac{1}{2}$.)

Spin 1 may result, however, from the coupling of two fermions with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ as in the case of the deuteron. If one considers spin to be angular momentum a proton and neutron may couple to form spin 0, but this has a higher energy than spin 1 because of spin dependent terms in the nucleon-nucleon interaction (2). In forming the Schrodinger equation for two fermions (2) one uses R_{cm} and r_1-r_2 where r_1 represents one nucleon and r_2 the other. As a result, one has $\exp(i p_{cm} R_{cm})$ which has the appearance of a free particle wavefunction. The deuteron itself is a composite particle with a certain mass. One may immediately argue that ((1a)) and ((1b)) should apply to the cm and ask why one cannot reproduce the argument of 3-space recognition for the cm? In other words why isn't the center of mass associated with a spin of $\frac{1}{2}$. First of all, each nucleon contains its own spin $\frac{1}{2}$ because each have 3-space recognition. Given the coupling of spin (angular momenta add as vectors, although with quantization) to 1 suggests some overall independent 3-space recognition is lost by the center of mass i.e. by the deuteron object. This seems to follow from the fact (like in the photon case) that for any axis, there are 1 and -1 projections, but also a third projection in a perpendicular direction. Thus, there does not seem to be 3-space independence. If one only thinks of spin being linked to angular momentum, the idea of 3-space independence does not arise, but we argue that it seems to exist, but full 3-space independence seems to only be manifest for spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

For He3, there are three fermions of spin $\frac{1}{2}$, but the overall object has spin $\frac{1}{2}$, thus we argue that it too would have full independent 3-space recognition. We argued above that spin matrices take the place of basis vectors and so the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case is the one which seems to represent the delta(ij) metric i.e. lead to $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$. Other spin cases do not. For example in the photon case, one has the Poynting vector $E \times B$ so ϵ_{ijk} is a little different (i.e. contains antisymmetric indices). Thus, we argue that spin is related to a kind of spatial geometry or spatial recognition.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I of this note we argued that $-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \{ A = -Et + px \}$ could be modified to bring in considerations of p_x, p_y, p_z i.e. flow in all 3 directions, not just in the overall direction of the vector p . This seems to be a completely general idea, but apparently is not. Normally one introduces basis vectors e_i ($i=1,2,3$) such that $e_i e_i = 1$. Here one has an operator equation and the basis vectors are replaced with basis operators i.e. matrices. Squaring a p vector which $-id/dx_j$ and a_j (matrix) operators should yields $-d/dx d/dx -d/dy d/dy -d/dz d/dz$ i.e. the absence of basis operators as in the Klein-Gordon equation. As P. Dirac showed, the 4x4 matrices contain the Pauli matrices and only apply to spin $1/2$, not to any spin even though 3-space recognition seems to be a general idea. Thus, we argue that it is not a general idea i.e. spin $\frac{1}{2}$ independently recognizes 3-space by having spin up or down in any spatial direction. If one examines a photon, the spin is 1 and there is spin up (1,1) and down

(1,-1) in a plane perpendicular to motion, but (1,0), which is not manifest, is not in this plane. Thus, two axes and not one are linked to projections along a particular x,y,z axis. This seems to break the 3-space independence.

In this note, we consider He4 which has spin 0. Like the spin 0 case of two nucleons, it seems that all space recognition is lost because one nucleon's projection cancels that of the other. Thus spatial recognition in a particular dimension seems to involve being able to have spin up or down in that direction and no inclusion of another dimension. Spin 1 immediately breaks this idea by having a projection (1,0) in another direction. Thus, linking spin matrices to the usual 3-space orthogonal basis vectors seems to apply to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ which holds for electrons and nucleons, but also for other objects such as He3. In other words, we argue that spin is not just an intrinsic angular momentum, but is somehow linked with 3-space recognition and geometry.

References

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